

Risk Governance and Financial Performance: Rural Banking Experience

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Abstract

The paper's goal is to examine the effect of risk governance variables on firm financial performance, with a specific focus on the rural banking sector. The paper used panel data of 67 rural banks in Ghana from 2014 to 2018. The study used the population-average model (PAM) as an estimation technique. The study's findings indicate that the size of the risk committee, its independence, and the presence of a chief risk officer have a positive and significant relationship with the financial performance of the rural banking sector. As a result, the introduction of risk governance in the banking sector tends to improve rural banking's financial performance. The study further reveals that the standard governance measures commonly used in the literature on corporate governance and its impact on performance may not fully capture the relevance of banks' governance structures.

Keywords: *risk governance, risk committee, financial performance, rural, and banking.*

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper aims to examine the impact of risk governance on firm financial performance in emerging markets, with a specific reference to the rural banking sector. We investigate whether the recent call to form a risk governance committee at the board level affects firm financial performance. Following several corporate scandals that hit the financial sector of the global economy, researchers have questioned the monitoring role of financial institutions' boards. In the past decade, the issue of risk governance has received growing global attention, following the 2008 global financial crisis (Almania, 2019). One of the contributing factors, that led to the global financial crisis was the lack of monitoring and risk oversight (Gontarek, 2017). Before the financial crisis, there was a lack of proper board-level risk oversight, which has piqued the interest of academia and practitioners in risk governance studies. As a result, researchers are examining the composition and size of the board-level risk committee as one aspect of risk governance. These variables should be significant means through which a firm can improve committee-monitoring effectiveness and achieve better performance. Despite the literature debate highlighting the significance of risk committee characteristics, there is a lack of agreement regarding their influence on performance.

Several studies have attempted to establish the relationship between risk committee attributes and performance (Ballaglia, Gallo, & Gaziano, 2014; Battaglia & Gallo, 2015; Berezints, Yulia, & Cherkasskaya, 2017; Erin, Bamigboye, & Arumona, 2020). These studies have yielded mixed results, with some agreeing and others disagreeing with significant theories of risk committees (Elamer & Benyazid, 2018). However, the literature lacks a compelling explanation for the mixed and inconclusive findings. It is possible that this inadequacy in the literature prevents a comprehensive understanding of

the effectiveness of risk committee characteristics. Furthermore, the difficulty in measuring risk committee size, independence, and performance may contribute to the inconclusive findings. Prior studies do not account for the variation in risk committee size relative to firm size. The risk committee's independence also varies depending on the size of the committee and the firm. This flaw in the measurement is likely to change any link between performance and committee size, as well as the committee's independence. This means that the interpretation is harmful for both policy and theory (Badu & Appiah, 2017). Again, the presence of a Chief Risk Officer (CRO) is a critical factor if the risk governance at the board level is going to be effective in managing risk and improving performance. However, there is a dearth of empirical studies investigating the presence of CRO, and the possibility of adding value to shareholders through risk governance at the board level is limited.

Despite the growing importance of risk governance around the globe, research on risk governance has focused on advanced economies and the established market, empirical evidence points out that there are scanty studies that examine risk governance composition (Jiang, 2020; Gontarek, 2017). Nigeria is the only country in sub-Saharan Africa where researchers have examined risk governance (Erin, Asiriwa, Olojede, Ajetunmobi, & Usman, 2018; Erin, Bamigboye, & Arumona, 2020). Apart from these two studies, there appears to be no other study that specifically focusses on the attributes of risk committees in any Sub-Saharan country, either for country-specific or regional cross-country research. Given the differences in corporate governance codes, regulations, transparency, and structural changes exhibited in Sub-Saharan Africa compared to other parts of the world, as well as the unique characteristics of each economic block, this study will present a compelling case for Africa.

In Africa, Ghana presents a unique case for examination in context because, before the Basel III recommendation for banks to constitute risk committees at the board level, Ghana had promulgated a corporate governance code in 2011 just after the financial crisis. The new Banking Act came into force in 2016, where the law emphasised risk governance in the banking sector, yet the banking sector has suffered a crisis between 2017 and 2018 in the face of regulatory and supervisory interventions. This investigation focusses on how this intervention regarding risk governance affected performance in the Ghanaian banking sector. Recent research on performance in Ghana also looks at it from the point of view of the audit committee, corporate governance, external and internal audit, and risk management (Yusheng, Bawuah, Djan, & Kuutol, 2019; Stephen, Djan, Bawuah, Halidu, & Kuutol, 2015; Kuutol & Agyemang, 2015; Badu, 2020) (Badu & Appiah, 2017). However, despite its role in monitoring performance, risk governance receives insufficient attention. Furthermore, studies on risk governance are required for the financial sectors in Africa, especially when evidence from developed markets fails to be a proxy for emerging economies (Atuahene, 2016).

Uniquely, this study seeks to contribute to risk governance literature in different ways. In the first place, the study measures risk committee size and independence by accounting for the size of the firm, unlike previous studies that measured committee size by absolute number and committee independence by the percentage of independence. Secondly, the study presents evidence from the rural banking sector, of which, to date and to the best of our knowledge, no evidence exists with respect to risk governance and performance. Finally, the study examines the banking sector following reforms, providing new insights into risk governance and firm performance from an Africa and emerging market perspective. The importance of this study to the Ghanaian banking sector and other emerging economies motivates us to produce and present our findings, which could potentially foster sustainable growth in the banking sector and influence policy debate.

The study's findings demonstrate that risk committee size, risk committee independence, and the presence of a CRO are all positively and significantly related to firm performance. Furthermore, it was revealing to observe that the standard governance measures commonly employed in the literature on corporate governance and its impact on performance may not fully capture the relevance of a bank's governance structure. We arrange the remainder of the paper as follows: In Section 2, we present a literature review on theoretical and empirical perspectives and hypotheses development. Section 3 defines the research design, the data utilised for the study, and the methods of measurement employed in the study. Finally, Section 4 presents the result of the study, discussion, conclusions, contribution, and limitations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Perspective

Several studies have shown that the risk governance process is contingent on several variables for it to be successful (Sharma, Lawrence, & Lowe, 2010). The literature argues that most studies mirror the early contingency theory research in management and accounting, suggesting that several contingency factors are associated with controls and governance (Erin et al., 2020). In the 1950s, contingency theory focused primarily on effectiveness and organizational structure (Diskson, 2001). Fried Fraser and Sharper, who were the early founders of the theory, were of the view that firm performance is contingent on both internal and external factors, and such factors help shape the firm's existence and behaviour. Beasley, Clune, & Hermanson (2005) asserted that contingency theory has broadened its scope beyond management and accounting literature to encompass finance and risk in recent decades.

The majority of research in this regard views contingency theory concerning firm performance in determining the risk governance process (Andries & Brown, 2014; Ellul & Yerramilli, 2013). According to the authors, the tendency to minimize performance or firm value destroyed during financial or economic distress justifies the real need for risk governance processes. Additionally, organisational resource planning, size, and governance structure have the potential to affect the risk governance practices of the firm (Aabo, Fraser, & Simkins, 2005). A number of research pieces of evidence have shown that in the context of contingency theory, there is a link between risk governance and the contemporary structure of corporate governance (Mikes & Kaplan, 2015). They argued that effective risk management practices are contingent on governance issues such as risk committees, board independence, board financial expertise, and effective board monitoring. Therefore, researchers have shown the significance of contingency theory in the process of risk governance (Erin et al. 2020).

On one hand, risk governance acceptability is contingent on the appointment of the Chief Risk Officer (CRO) and other risk specialist functions (Beasley, Clune, & Hermanson, 2005; Bromiley, McShane, Nair, & Rostambekov, 2015), which point to internal factors. They argued that because risk governance is an emerging area, it requires a new design of organisational responsibility. One major factor that indicates effective risk governance is the appointment of a CRO, whose assignment is a specialised managerial portfolio with responsibility for risk coordination. Conversely, some studies contend that firms view contingency theory through the lens of external factors, which in turn shape their decisions. The global financial and localised financial crisis impact has brought to bear the agitation from external factors like regulatory bodies, investors, and other external stakeholders on the need for adopting a more holistic risk management approach (Erin et al., 2020). Both internal and external factors are important as determinants of organizational structure and effectiveness, as far as contingency theorists are concerned (Stulz, 2018). Therefore, we cannot underestimate the importance of the contingency approach to the risk governance process.

2.2 Risk governance and performance

According to Harrington, Niehaus, & Risko (2005), risk governance serves as an integrated system that identifies and measures all risk exposures, including operational and competitive risk. Therefore, risk governance is an integrated risk management approach that aids in the identification and assessment of collective risk affecting firm performance (Meulbroek, 2002). Therefore, the goal of risk governance is to comprehensively manage and reduce risks that have the potential to destroy profitability. A well-integrated and robust approach to risk management that is centralized yields better results than fragmented approaches. Researchers have described risk governance as a corporate-wide approach to managing in totality the liability structure of the firm to maximise profitability (Verbrugge et al., 2003). According to this perspective, centralised risk management in firms makes risk management more offensive (proactive) than defensive.

Erin et al. (2020) have extensively discussed the literature on the significance of performance on corporate governance, capital structure, and risk management. Erin et al., 2020; Waweku & Kisaka, 2010 have observed that the risk governance system has a stronger tendency to improve financial performance in risk management. Financial performance serves as an indicator of how well firm management is adding value to shareholders' wealth. Every firm's success primarily hinges on its ability to manage its risk structure and implement an effective risk governance framework to generate value. Researchers have shown that risk governance structure effectiveness will lead to overall risk reduction, thereby potentially increasing wealth creation for shareholders (Beasley et al. 2005). Following Beasley et al. (2005), we deduce that a firm's ability to implement a holistic risk management strategy or policy direction helps firms make more profit, thereby increasing shareholder wealth.

2.3 Risk Governance Framework

The literature establishes certain risk governance determinants that an organization must possess to ensure a robust risk governance framework (Erin et al. 2020). Therefore, without an established determinants-risk governance framework, it is destined to fail or be weak and may not make a meaningful contribution to the organization as anticipated.

2.3.1 Presence of Chief Risk Officer (CRO)

The appointment of a CRO is a major determinant factor for the risk governance framework. Studies have shown a significant positive relationship between the risk governance framework and the appointment of a chief risk officer (Beasley et al. 2005). Other studies (Yazid, Hussein, & Wan Daud, 2011) support this finding by demonstrating that the appointment of a Chief Risk Officer (CRO) influences the risk governance system of any firm. The ultimate role of CRO is to fashion out a functional and integrated risk management framework for all levels within the firm (Erin et al., 2020). Empirical evidence has shown that the presence of CRO is significant in managing risk and contributing to improved performance (Erin et al., 2020; Liebenberg & Hoyt, 2003). On the contrary, Elamer & Benyazid (2018) found that the presence of CRO influences performance negatively. They argued that the presence of the CRO constrains management's ability to make excessive and decisive risk-taking decisions, thereby affecting performance negatively. Therefore, the evidence from developing countries supports this claim. Evidence from Asia indicates a negative relationship between the presence of CRO and performance, whereas evidence from Africa indicates a reverse relationship. Based on these findings, we hypothesise:

H₁: The presence of the Chief Risk Officer positively related to performance.

2.3.2 Board Risk Committee Size

According to Ng, Chong, & Ismail (2012), the board bears the ultimate responsibility for overseeing risk management and risk in any firm. According to Nakano & Nyuyen (2012), in the recent trend of risk management and corporate governance, firms have increased the percentage of independent directors and diversity of those directors to enhance board performance. Erin et al. 2020 underscore the importance of establishing an independent committee within the board to supervise risk management policies and formulate strategies. In some countries, this risk governance variable is a legal requirement, while in others, it is a regulatory demand. (Ng, Chong, & Ismail, 2012) Empirical evidence has shown that financial institutions with large risk committee sizes tend to perform better in terms of accounting profitability (Battaglia & Gallo, 2015). Ellul & Yerramilli (2013) also noted that banks with robust independent risk committees are less vulnerable to risk, and when a bank avoids risk, its profitability may not suffer as it would otherwise. In the context of this study, the Bank of Ghana has prescribed the institutionalisation of risk committees to banks, taking reference from Section 56 of Act 930 of 2016. We have a firm belief that such a committee will help monitor, reduce risk, and improve the performance of banking firms. Thus, we hypothesized that:

H₂: The size of the board risk committee is positively associated with performance.

2.3.3 Independence of the Board Risk Committee

Due to the complexity of several risks facing financial institutions, the aftermath of the global financial crisis has led to a significant number of financial firms establishing risk governance committees for risk monitoring and management (Hines & Peters, 2015). Risk committee independence is critical to the risk management activities of every firm (Eckles, Hoyt, & Miller, 2014). Sound corporate governance principles initiate every risk governance process (Erin et al., 2020). As a result, the inclusion of an independent person in the risk committee will enhance the firm's risk culture, risk disclosure, and risk construction (Okoye, Adetiloye, Olayinka, & Evbuomwan, 2017; Bromiley et al., 2014). Risk committee independence helps in the monitoring of firms' activities and identification of varieties of risk within the business setting (Aebi, Sabato, & Schmid, 2012). Given the nature of risk governance mechanisms in risk management, Barakat & Hussainey (2013) expect the process to lessen the negative impact on firms' performance. Walker (2009) suggested that financial institutions establish risk committees to control risk and prevent excessive risk-taking. We believe that a risk committee with a higher level of independence facilitates better monitoring of the firm's risk situation and allows management to question decisions that could potentially undermine the firm's performance. Therefore, we hypothesise that

H₃: Performance positively correlates with the risk committee's independence.

2.4 Empirical Review

Risk governance has emerged as a new discipline in the past decade, attracting the attention of risk management, accounting, and finance professionals. Many authors have written about various perspectives on risk. Several of these studies focused on the emerging financial industry. Erin et al. (2020) examines risk governance and financial performance: an empirical analysis. The study uses 50 firms from Nigeria's financial sector from 2013-2017. They used correlation and regression analysis to analyse panel data. Risk governance variables include board risk committee size, board risk committee activism, chief risk officer presence, board risk committee independence, and enterprise risk management as explanatory variables and return on assets as the dependent variable. The study revealed that most of the risk governance variables (board risk committee activism, chief risk officer presence, board risk committee independence, and enterprise risk management) have a significant and positive

impact on the financial performance of the study firms. The study indicated that these variables have the potential to significantly enhance the performance of Nigeria's financial environment today.

Erin et al. (2018) conducted an investigation to answer the question, "Does risk governance impact bank performance?" The Nigerian Banking Sector provides evidence, encompassing 11 banks from 2012 to 2016. The study utilised correction and regression analysis on panel data, ensuring a fixed effect. The study employed variables as proxies for risk governance, which included the presence of a chief risk officer, the centrality of the chief risk officer, the independence and activism of the board risk committee, the independence of the board of directors, and the enterprise risk management score, in addition to other control variables. We used return on assets (the dependent variable) as a proxy for measuring performance. The findings showed that all explanatory variables, except Chief Risk Officer Centrality, have a significant positive impact on the performance of listed Nigerian banks. Therefore, the authors recommended regulatory authorities should ensure compliance with the risk governance framework.

Badu, Board Composition and Firm Performance: Does Board Monitoring Intensity Mediate the Relationship in Emerging Markets? 2020) The study aims to empirically examine the relationship between risk governance and firm performance, using data from 21 Italian listed banks from 2005 to 2013. The study's findings showed that the chief risk officer's presence, the board of directors' independence level at the risk committee meeting, and the experience of the risk committee represented risk governance, while return on equity and return on assets served as dependent variables. The finding revealed that while some of the risk governance has a significant relationship with firm performance, others do not. As a result, they suggest that the study provides an opportunity for further studies on risk governance and other topics. Battaglia & Gallo (2015) examine risk governance and Asia bank performance: an empirical investigation over the financial crisis. From 2007 to 2011, they conducted a study on Chinese and Indian listed banks, focusing on variables such as risk committee size and meetings. They discovered that the inclusion of risk committee size and meetings in the model generally rendered the standard board variables irrelevant. The study found that risk committee size and risk committee meetings have a positive relationship with accounting measures of performance.

Zemzem & Kacem (2014) investigated the impact of risk management and governance on the performance of financial institutions in Tunisia with a sample size of 17 Tunisian banks between 2001 and 2011. Their result showed a negative relationship between risk governance and firm performance. In line with studies by Mollah, Hassan, Al Farooque, & Mobarek (2014), the studies failed to consider significant risk governance variables as recommended by the International Risk Governance Council (IRGC) in their model.

Ellul & Yerramilli (2012) examine the effect of strong risk control and governance on the performance of 74 US banks operating from 2006 to 2011. Ellul & Yerramilli (2012) measured risk governance, which included the presence of a risk department, the appointment of a chief risk officer, the implementation of ERM, the audit committee, and board risk independence. The findings showed that the majority of risk governance variables significantly enhanced the performance of the firms under study. They also observed that strong risk control mechanisms tend to reduce US banks' risk-taking behavior.

McShane et al. (2011) critically examine the impact of risk governance on financial performance using 82 insurance firms in China. The study measured performance and risk governance using return on asset and S&P risk rating, taking into account control variables such as firm size, growth opportunities, cash

flow volatility, and leverage. According to the study, the risk governance process has not improved the financial performance of U.S. insurance firms. The authors were of the opinion that firms with a stronger risk governance structure are taking greater risk in the area of their core capabilities. Mongiardino & Plath (2010) examine risk governance and performance after the financial crisis, taking evidence from 25 large banks in Europe. They discovered that the performance of large European banks has only slightly improved since the financial crisis.

Based on the aforementioned empirical studies, we found that risk governance positively and significantly impacts firm performance (Erin et al., 2020; 2018; Battaglia & Gallo, 2015; Ellul & Yerramilli, 2012; McShane et al., 2011; Mongiardino & Plath, 2010). However, other studies, such as Cavezzali & Garddenal, 2015; Zenzem & Kacem, 2014; Mollah et al., 2014, revealed that risk governance had no effect on performance. Based on the aforementioned empirical review, we formulated the following hypothesis:

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This paper uses content analysis and panel data analysis to examine the impact of risk governance on performance between 2014 and 2018 in the financial sector, specifically the rural banking sector. 144 rural banks make up the study population, and 67 rural banks comprise the sample size due to their availability of data for the study. The data variable was derived from the firm's annual reports. Due to the role banks play in the stability of economies and prevention of systematic collapse of financial institutions, we examine the banking sector with a focus on rural banks in Ghana. Risk governance mechanisms are crucial for the survival of the banking system in our current era, making it crucial for this study to critically examine the relationship between risk governance and performance. We shall employ descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression models to analyse the study result.

3.1 Variable operationalisation

The operational variables used in this study range from the dependent variable to explanatory variables, some of which have been employed in previous risk governance studies.

Table 1: Operationalization of Variables

Variables	Symbol	Operationalization	Expected sign
Return on Assets	ROA	This is proxy by net income divided by total assets	
Return on Equity	ROE	This is proxy by net income divided by total Equity	
Presence of chief risk Officer	PCRO	This is measured as a dummy variable; we score one 1 for firms with CRO designation otherwise 0.	Positive (+)
Independence of Board risk committee	IBRC	This is the proportion of non-executive directors on the committee divided by the total number of risk committee members. Further adjusting it with size of the firm.	Positive (+)
Board Risk committee size	BRCS	Total members on the committee as measured by Erin et al. (2020) measure this. This measurement is modified to be redefined as the total number of the member on the committee relative the size of the firm	Positive (+)

Independent Board of Directors	IBOD	This is the proportion of non-executive directors on the board divided by the total number of risk total board members.	Positive (+)
Board Size	BOSI	This is measured by the number of Board member held in the financial year	Positive (+)
Board meetings	BOMG	This is measured by the number of times meeting held in the financial year	Positive (+)
Firm size	FISI	This is measured by the log of total asset held in a financial year	Positive (+)

3.2 Model specification

The model's development draws on conceptual issues reviewed in the literature. Given the dataset, panel data analysis is an efficient tool to use since the sampled data are time series and cross-sectional. As suggested by Battaglia & Gallo (2015), bank-specific features such as management style and quality, market perceptions, business strategy, and the like help take into account the unobservable and consistent heterogeneity of the panel data set. You can use several linear models for the panel data. The most commonly used are the Fixed Effect Model (FEM) and Random Effect Model (REM), of which the two have fundamental differences. The main method of estimation is the generalised least squares (GLS) REM technique. This method can only be strong if there is first-order autoregressive disturbance (if any) in the cross-sectional and unbalanced panels, as well as heteroscedasticity between panels. The presence of unobserved banks' fixed effect primarily suggests FEM estimation (Wooldridge, 2002), provided that the Hausman test validates the assumption.

The study conducted a Hausman specification test to aid in determining whether to choose Random Effect Model (REM) or Fixed Effect Model (FEM) for the panel regression analysis. In the Hausman specification test, the decision rule dictates accepting the null hypothesis when the p-value exceeds the 0.05 Mackinnon value. However, Gujarati & Porter (2009) suggest rejecting the hypothesis when the p-value is less than 0.05. If we reject the hypothesis, the fixed effect model becomes appropriate. Following the Hausman test below in Table 2, it indicates that the p-value is less than 0.05, so the appropriate model for the study is FEM.

Table 2: Hausman specification Test

HAUSMAN SPECIFICATION TEST		
Test of Cross-Section Random Effects		
Test Summary	Chi. Sq. Stat.	p-Value
Cross-Section	40.9572	0.000

The current study concludes that FEM estimation is not suitable for two major reasons. First, we can't use fixed effect regression to estimate the time-invariant governance variables in this study because it might mess up the "within transformation" or "time demeaning" process of the variables in FEM. Even though GLS REM could be used as an alternative to FEM, we were encouraged to use the population-average model (PAM), because, in the presence of a panel characterised by few firms and the time horizon being short, the estimation of REM could be affected by the scarcity in the randomness of the variables, while the OLS can be more safely implemented. The regressors in the PAM assume exogenous and simply account for the error as μ_{it} rather than decomposing the error as $\alpha_i + \varepsilon_{it}$.

Then:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha + \beta X_{it} + \mu_{it} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Just like REM estimators, consistency of the estimators requires that the regressors be uncorrelated with μ_{it} .

We rated our variables at 5% to prevent extreme values from distorting our study's results, despite the presence of large outliers. 5% winorizing involves assigning to out The 5% winsorizing method assigns values to outliers that fall beyond the 5th and 95th percentiles, thereby limiting their influence on the regression. We did not rely on a specific treatment of the outliers; we equally categorize them at 1% and 10%, ensuring that the results did not differ from the main results. At the bank level, our observations clearly cluster. Given the potential presence of the same bank across different years, it may be appropriate to adjust the error for the same intermediary over time. By doing so, we obtained standard errors that are robust to heteroscedasticity.

The model below captures risk governance variables identified in the study literature. Equation (2) expresses our baseline econometric model, from which we estimate each profitability.

$$Y_{it} = \beta_{0it} + \beta_1 PCRO_{it} + \beta_2 BRCS_{it} + \beta_3 IBRC_{it} + \beta_4 IBOD_{it} + \beta_5 BOSI_{it} + \beta_6 BOAC_{it} + \beta_7 FISI_{it} + \mu_{it} \dots (2)$$

β_0 = This is regarded as a constant in the equation, others are the intercepts of the regression line.

β_{1-7} = is the slope of the regression line or coefficient.

μ = Error term;

i = Firm

t = period or year

3.3 Endogeneity issues

Endogeneity is a problem that comes up a lot in governance studies and makes interpretation harder (Battaglia & Gallo, 2015). Because firm governance structure and performance are determined by endogeneity, it's possible for relationships between board characteristics and performance to be more than they seem. However, this issue is less likely to pose problems in the research context due to two key factors. In the first instance In the first place, Pathan and Faff (2013) said that the crisis period is like an experiment because it gives us a favorable chance to test the link between boards and performance in a way that doesn't depend on variables related to Between 2013 and 2016, the onset of a power shortage, popularly known as 'dumsor' in Ghana, plunged the Ghanaian economy and banking sector into a crisis. A significant crisis in the banking sector emerged in 2017-2018. Secondly, Wintoki, Linck, & Netter (2012) assert that governance studies must control dynamic endogeneity as a significant source of endogeneity to achieve unbiased results. However, Adams & Mehran (2012) asserted that dynamic endogeneity is less problematic for banks due to the use of past performance as a proxy for management capability, which does not impact board size or composition.

4. FINDINGS

The main objective of this paper is to examine the impact of risk governance and practices on financial performance, with a specific focus on the rural banking sector. This section presents the empirical findings related to descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression results of the study.

Table 3: Descriptive statistics

	Regressand		Interest variables			Control variables			
	ROE	ROA	PCRO	BRCS	IBRC	BOSI	IBOD	BOAC	FISI
Mean	0.1876	0.1398	0.89	4.85	0.546	7.59	4.80	3.75	5.457
Minimum	-0.1247	-0.0907	0	4	0.33	6	4	2	4.942
Maximum	0.2948	0.1814	1	6	0.60	9	6	5	9.334
Std Dev.	0.3547	0.1254	0.341 2	0.0947	0.1004	0.4174	0.0505	0.1278	1.490
Obs	335	335	335	335	335	335	335	335	335

Table 3 above presents the descriptive statistics for the variables entered in the model. According to the risk governance variables, 89% of firms in the rural banking sector have employed a Chief Risk Officer to oversee the risk management architecture and related risk matters. This indicates that the boards have taken risk governance seriously and have established a key individual responsible for the risk management architecture, ensuring they receive well-informed reports to aid in their decision-making process. This creates an enabling environment for the boards to be proactive in their risk management assessment. The average size of the risk committee in rural banks is five members. Out of the five members on the risk committee, 55% are nonexecutive directors. This indicates that there is greater independence of the risk committee in the rural banking sector. We, therefore, state that higher risk committee independence will bring more board monitoring intensity to the rural banking sector in Ghana. The average board size is 8 people, while the average number of independent board directors is 5. The rural banking sector in Ghana exhibits approximately 63% board independence. The results of board activism show that members can convene an average of four times during the financial year (quarterly) to oversee management activities, including risk management. The study also included standard governance measures, which are commonly used in corporate governance literature, as a control variable to assess their relevance. se.

Table 4: Correlation Matrix

	ROA	ROE	PCRO	BRCS	IBRC	BOSI	IBOD	BOAC	FISI
ROA	1								
ROE	0.8542	1							
PCRO	0.3143	0.1472	1						
BRCS	0.4298	0.3986	0.2003	1					
IBRC	0.5011	0.4789	0.3309	0.4207	1				
BOSI	0.2705	0.3974	0.2821	0.4977	0.5917	1			
IBOD	0.0847	0.1217	0.3791	0.2312	0.5642	0.6147	1		
BOAC	0.2786	0.1974	0.6903	0.4276	0.3177	0.3989	-0.1998	1	
FISI	0.4431	0.5587	-0.1473	-0.0994	0.5502	0.4025	0.0948	0.2874	1

Table 4 above shows the correlation matrix for the variables under consideration in this study. The results indicate that all risk governance variables have a positive correlation with performance measures, standard corporate governance variables, and firm size. According to the evidence presented in Table 4 above, the risk governance process is most likely to influence firm performance in the Ghanaian rural banking sector. The positive association between the presence of a chief risk officer and performance indicators implies that firms with a CRO are likely to deploy sophisticated risk infrastructure to combat potential risks that may negatively affect the firm's financial assets. The size of the risk governance committee, its independence, the size of the board, and the level of activism all have a significant impact on the firm's financial performance.

Table 5: Regression Analysis

Independent Variables	MODEL 1: ROA	MODEL 2: ROE
Interest Variables		
PCRO	0.3894***	0.2147***
BRCS	0.2978***	0.3004***
IBRC	0.2005***	0.1341**
Control Variables		
BOSI	0.1076	0.1746
IBOD	0.1256	0.0911
BOAC	0.1998**	0.2581**
FISI	0.2341***	0.1487**
Model Statistics		
R-squared	0.4759	0.3991
Adjusted R-squared	0.4199	0.3682
F-statistics	11.81***	14.47***

*** denotes significant at 1%, ** denotes significant at 5%, and * denotes significant at 10%.

The regression results suggest a strong, significant relationship between the explanatory variables and the dependent variable, as indicated by the F-statistics. Furthermore, the analysis shows that the risk governance variables and the control variables account for 47.59% and 39.91% of the total changes in ROA and ROE, respectively. The models are well fitted, given the R-squares and the statistical significance of the F-statistics.

Table 5 concentrates on the Ghanaian rural banking sector, examining key risk governance variables and their impact on the sector's financial performance. The study results show a positive and significant relationship between all the risk governance variables (PCRO, BRCS, and IBRC) and financial performance. Generally, in the Ghanaian banking sector, risk governance variables have a significant impact on financial performance. The findings support accepting the stated hypotheses.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Financial inclusion, growth opportunities, and poverty and inequality persist in the absence of well-functioning financial institutions (World Bank, 2007). In their studies of rural India, Burgess and Pande (2005) revealed that the establishment of banks in rural areas led to structural change and poverty reduction. We cannot understate the role rural banks play in financial inclusion and its impact on economic and social wellbeing in rural societies. In this regard, the survival and sustainability of the rural banking sector are of paramount interest to policymakers. Proper risk governance and excellent corporate governance are therefore essential to rural banks' survival. This paper aims to examine the effect of risk governance variables on firm financial performance, with a specific focus on the rural banking sector.

The above-mentioned findings imply key implications for risk governance on corporate sustainability. The positive relationship between the presence of a Chief Risk Officer (CRO) and financial performance suggests that employing a CRO is as important as having a board presence in the day-to-day running of the banking sector's business. The presence of a Chief Risk Officer (CRO) not only measures management's risk-taking adventure, but also addresses and mitigates the emerging risks that today's banking industry faces. This finding is consistent with the current trend in literature, indicating that hiring CRO tends to reduce the impact of risk on the organisation (Erin et al., 2020; 2018; Soliman & Adams, 2017). Therefore, today's banking business cannot discount the CRO portfolio. Contrary to this finding, Elamer & Benyazid (2018) observed that the presence of a CRO reduces performance because of excessive management monitoring. Perhaps they found a negative relationship because the cost of running risk governance in the study setting outweighs its benefit.

Furthermore, the size of the risk committee impacts its financial performance. Previous studies have measured the board risk committee size by the total number of members on the risk committee (Erin et al., 2020; 2018) and have found no relationship. Because the researchers believe that the size of the firm should determine the size of the committee, we adjusted the committee size to match the size of the firm. Contrary to the findings of Erin et al. (2020), our result showed that risk committee size has a significant positive relationship with financial performance in the rural banking sector. This implies that considering the firm's size when forming the risk committee is crucial for its impact on financial performance. Equally, the board risk committee's independence reveals a significant and positive relationship with financial performance. This indicates that since a majority of 55% of the committee members are independent directors, they are able to assess management strategy concerning risk management and hold them to account for their executive actions. This study's findings are consistent with those of Soliman and Adams (2017). Therefore, we suggest that the size of the firm should influence the formation of a board risk committee in the banking sector.

As observed by Battaglia & Gallo (2015), the bank board variables seem to have a limited impact on the financial performance in terms of board size and board independence. As expected, the size and presence of independent directors may not have a direct impact on performance until the board convenes for a meeting and discusses reports with detailed accounts, which then shapes policy direction. This may eventually go a long way towards influencing performance. The independent director's insignificance highlights the characteristics of directors appointed to rural banking boards. Additionally, the insignificant size of the board suggests that the size of the board does not matter in the rural banking sector. This finding is in sharp contrast with the existing literature in Ghana, which uses standard board-level variables (Badu, 2020; Badu & Appiah, 2017). Adding risk governance variables to the model, which usually makes the standard board's variables useless, is in line with what other studies have found (Battaglia & Gallo, 2015; Aebi et al., 2012).

5.2 Conclusion

The study focused on the Ghanaian rural banking sector, examining the impact of risk governance on financial performance. This study has key implications for risk governance practices and corporate sustainability in the Ghanaian banking industry. We studied selected 67 rural banks between 2014 and 2018 by using content analysis to derive the data for the analysis. The study revealed that all the risk governance variables used in this study have significant and positive relationships with financial performance. We, therefore, conclude that risk governance has the opportunity to maximise (add value to) shareholders' wealth. Risk managers play a critical role in the financial stability of the banking industry, ensuring national stability, and a bank should not undervalue their role to enjoy the goodwill of its stakeholders.

This study provides critical and original insight into risk governance variables that affect the Ghanaian banking sector's financial performance. In sub-Saharan Africa, particularly emerging economies, we have contributed to the development of literature in the areas of risk governance, risk management, and financial performance. This study makes a big difference because it measures the size of the board risk committee. The variable was changed to account for the size of the firm, and the results showed a significant relationship. This is different from other studies done in Sub-Saharan Africa (Erin et al., 2020). The findings revealed that risk governance factors are important determinants of a bank's performance. This finding will be of interest to policymakers and regulators in developing economies where risk governance is not well exercised to justify greater interventions. Finally, Battaglia & Gallo (2015) concluded that the standard governance measures commonly used in the literature on corporate governance and its valuation impact on performance may not adequately describe the relevance of banks' governance structures. Instead, they have upheld the significance of the call for the introduction of risk governance in both developed and emerging markets.

This study focused on Ghana's rural banking sector. This paper has established the foundation for empirical research on risk governance in Ghana, specifically focussing on industries beyond banking. It is critical to conduct regional studies in the field of risk governance and financial performance, in line with studies conducted in other sub-Saharan African nations, such as Nigeria. Furthermore, testing the effectiveness of risk governance will add more understanding to the current literature. The inclusion of risk governance variables such as the CRO's experience, the committee chair's experience, and committee members interlocking with the audit committee will help gain a better understanding of the risk governance process.

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